

Analysis on Open Data as a foundation for data-driven research

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Abstract

Open Science is a policy initiative that serves as a foundation for “Data-driven research,” and Open Data has been promoted in many countries. However, the current status of the use of publicly available data consisting of Open Data in new research activities and the impact of such use remains unclear. From this perspective, we analysed the Data Citation Index (DCI) published by Clarivate Inc., which is a comprehensive collection of research datasets and repositories. The results revealed that different countries and disciplines tend to show different trends in Open Data. In recent years, the number of data sets in repositories where researchers publish their data, regardless of the discipline, has increased dramatically, and researchers are publishing more data. Furthermore, there are some disciplines where data citation rates are not high, but the databases used are diverse.

Introduction: Data-driven research

Open Science (OS), a new research style in which sharing and utilizing data and findings from research activities in the academic community, is being promoted in many countries. OS is defined as “an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.” (UNESCO, 2021). Research activities that aggregate data sharing (Open Data) and perform big data analysis, one of the elements of OS, are referred to as “Data-driven research” (OECD, 2015). An OECD report suggests that the concept could be used in research activities as part of “Data-driven Innovation (DDI),” which is defined as “*the use of data and analysis to improve and foster products, processes, organizational practices, and markets.*” The developments in ICT have enabled the collection and use of big data, and innovations that deal with the data itself are expected.

In recent years, academia has faced the advent of “data-intensive scientific discovery,” which is considered the fourth paradigm of science. Even in disciplines that have not been data-intensive in the past, it is now possible to conduct research that uses data to perform simulations. Open Data is expected to become the foundation for data-driven research, stimulating research activities and improving cost-effectiveness. Previous studies have investigated whether data are publicly available in disciplines such as Genetics and Materials Science, where data sharing and use are considered active, and the motivations for publishing and using data (Bettina et al., 2017; Robinson-Garcia et al., 2015; Silvello, 2014; Suhr, 2020), however, the overall picture is not clear. There is a movement to promote the customary use of data citation in academia. To evaluate the effectiveness of Open Data promotion for data-driven research in the future, it is necessary to confirm the current status and diversity of data disclosure and use in each discipline, and to conduct an evaluation that considers the citation relationship of published data. Using a database of research data, this study clarifies how the current status of data publication and citation can be analyzed.

Analysis: Current status of Open Data and its utilization

Research questions

We set the following two questions. (1) Which countries and research disciplines are active for Open Data? (2) In which discipline is “Data-driven research” being activated by data disclosure? Regarding RQ1, the volume of Open Data is assumed to differ depending on the Open Data policy and its speed in each country. Similarly, the recognition of the importance of Open Data differs among research disciplines, which may lead to differences in the current status. Regarding RQ2, there may be disciplines in which research is conducted using publicly available data, while there may be those that do not rely on Open Data.

Analysis: Status of DCI registration data

This study uses the Data Citation Index (¹DCI) published by Clarivate since 2012. We used DCI bulk data obtained in March 2022 from Clarivate. This database contains over nine million data sets from more than 401 repositories, as well as information on the articles that cite them. In addition, the Web of Science (WoS) is used for papers that cite the data registered in the DCI (DCI-recorded data). In the early years of the publication of DCI, there have been analyses of the fields of the recorded data and their citations (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2015) and of the software in the DCI (Park et al., 2019). However, the current status of data publication and use in the context of recent developments in Open Data is unclear.

Table 1. Basic Information on DCI Recorded Data

Document type	Data set	Data study	Software	Repository
Type Overview	Single or consistent data set of collected data, research data, or software	Description stored in repository with research data or software	Software used in conducting the study	Databases containing research data and metadata
No. of databases	12,227,647	1,400,409	253,772	443
Citation(s)	1,012,547	294,251	53,453	11,592
Percentage of quotations (%)	73.8	21.4	3.8	0.8

In analyzing the DCI data, we provide an overview of the data content; as of 2020, there were 13,882,271 total records in the DCI and 1,371,848 WoS articles citing these data. “Data set” account for 88% of the total data types included in the DCI (Figure 1).

After reviewing the actual data recorded in the DCI, it is unclear what kind of data is to be included, and what data should be counted as “one case.” Therefore, to understand which datasets are recorded in DCI, the top 10 repositories with the most data sets recorded in 2019 with the highest number of data recorded are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Information of repositories for top 10 frequency 2019 data sets

	Repository name	No. of data entries	Organization	Year	Discipline	Summary
1	Zenodo	550,688	European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN)	2013	Science & Technology - Other Topics/Multidisciplinary Sciences	Open platform for researchers to freely share research data with anyone.
2	Figshare	224,254	Digital science	2011	Science & Technology - Other Topics/Multidisciplinary Sciences	An online, open-access repository where researchers can store and share their research findings, including figures, data sets, images, and videos.

¹<https://clarivate.com/ja/solutions/data-citation-index/>

3	BacDive	162,953	Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	2012	Microbiology	Bacterial meta-database providing phylogeny-related information on bacterial and archaeal biodiversity.
4	Barcode of Life Data System	102,910	Center for Biodiversity and Genomics (Canada)	2007	Genetics & Heredity/Biochemistry & Molecular Biology	Web platform dedicated to DNA barcodes.
5	European Nucleotide Archive	68,550	European Bioinformatics Institute	1980	Genetics & Heredity	Repository providing free and unlimited access to annotated DNA and RNA sequences.
6	Cambridge Structural Database	59,717	Cambridge Crystallographic Research Center	1965	Crystallography	Repository of 3D structural data for a wide range of organic, organometallic, and organometallic molecules, including molecules.
7	U.S. Census Bureau TIGER/Line Shapefiles	33,080	U.S. Census Bureau	2007	Geography	Spatial files extracted from the U.S. Census Bureau's MAF/TIGER database of roads, railroads, rivers, and other land features, as well as legal and statistical geographic areas.
8	Mendeley Data	31,812	Elsevier, Inc.	2015	Science & Technology - Other Topics/Multidisciplinary Sciences	Public Repository of Research Data for Researchers.
9	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS-KNAW)	20,103	Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW)/Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO)	2005	Geosciences, Multidisciplinary/ Social Sciences, Interdisciplinary/ Geology/ Humanities, Multidisciplinary/ Social Sciences - Other Topics/Arts & Humanities - Other Topics	Public Repository of Research Data for Researchers.
10	MassBank	16,079	Mass Spectrometry Society of Japan (MSSJ)	2006	Spectroscopy	Public repository designed to share mass spectrometry data for compound identification and structure elucidation with the scientific research community.

The top 10 repositories in terms of frequency include four repositories for researchers (1, 2, 8, 9). These include many figures and extensive data accompanying research articles. This is a situation not observed in previous analysis on DCI (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2015). The remaining six repositories contain data on individual DNA information from life sciences and biotechnology, geographic data from the United States, and chemical structure data in the tens to hundreds of thousands of items. These results indicate that Open Data are a mixture of different types, including data accompanying research papers, large amounts of field-specific data in repositories operated by specific research organizations, and survey data by government agencies.

Furthermore, since it has already been highlighted in the aforementioned previous study that most of the DCI citations are self-citations, we checked the WoS papers citing them for several samples of the data sets cited in 2015. We found that, especially in the case of data publication by individual researchers, data and figures accompanying such papers and stored in repositories were also treated as “citations.” Furthermore, we identified what appeared to be self-citations of the data (note that information that can systematically confirm whether the data are self-citations is not included in the DCI). Although 73.8% of the data sets were cited at least once, it is possible that self-citations account for a large proportion. However, considering that it reflects the situation where data accompanying papers are made publicly available, even if the number of self-citations is high, it can be viewed as an indicator that reflects the progress of data-driven research through the publication of data.

Analysis 1: Current status of data release and its use by country and research disciplines

To ascertain which countries and disciplines are actively publishing data for RQ1, we tabulated the number of databases and time-series changes in 10 major disciplines (Figures 1 and 2). For Figure 2, a three-year moving average was taken. Research disciplines are assigned to the repositories in which the data sets are contained.

Figure 1. No. of databases in 10 major disciplines

Figure 2. Auto-sequential changes in the no. of databases in 10 major disciplines

The most common disciplines in the DCI-recorded data set are Genetics & Heredity at 31.5%, followed by Multidisciplinary Sciences at 23.3%, Biochemistry & Molecular Biology at 19.6%, and Crystallography at 10.4%. A review of the chronological changes by disciplines reveals that all disciplines have been increasing since 2005, but Multidisciplinary Sciences have increased rapidly since 2015, while all other disciplines have been decreasing. The data categorized as Multidisciplinary Sciences are those published in repositories that allow researchers to publish data accompanying their papers, regardless of the disciplines, which also appear at the top of Table 2. In other words, the number of individual researchers releasing data to non-discipline-specific repositories has been increasing rapidly since around 2015; it is possible that some of the data sets that were previously published in discipline-specific repositories are now also being published in these repositories.

Next, we tabulated the number of data sets for each of the 10 major disciplines of each major country (Table 3). Note that the country of the creator of the data set is assigned to 2,058,624 data sets in total, which means that only 16.8% of the total data sets are assigned the name of the country. Therefore, the overall percentage of countries is not large.

Table 3. Number of data sets and share (%) of the 10 main disciplines for the 5 major countries

	USA	China	Japan	Germany	Norway	Other					
Genetics & Heredity	1,068,211	24	141,983	3	70,931	2	101,772	2	17,940	0	2,980,435
Multidisciplinary Sciences	38,943	1	17,330	0	5,675	0	12,714	0	87,065	3	3,076,184
Biochemistry & Molecular Biology	927,307	34	48,520	2	61,967	2	81,463	3	8,653	0	1,595,026
Crystallography	442	0	10	0	4	0	4	0	-	-	1,436,370
Geosciences, Multidisciplinary	26,109	3	78	0	207	0	1,027	0	59	0	796,346
Ecology	59,383	9	8	0	55	0	16	0	19	0	618,876
Geography	26,109	3	78	0	207	0	1,027	0	59	0	799,377
Microbiology	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	413,251
Environmental Sciences	64,168	6	28	0	82	0	125	0	48	0	1,004,335
Spectroscopy	7,416	4	310	0	33,776	17	9,782	5	4	0	149,954
Total	1,446,658		181,639		121,204		140,018		110,637		12,870,153

The U.S. has a 20-30% share in the Biochemistry & Molecular Biology and Genetics & Heredity disciplines. China has almost no data releases outside of the top three disciplines. For Spectroscopy, Japan has released the top 17% of the data sets. According to Table 2, the repository of Spectroscopy is operated by the Mass Spectrometry Society of Japan (MSSJ),

which is one of the disciplines where Open Data has advanced in Japan. In Norway, there is a particularly large amount of data in the disciplines of Multidisciplinary Sciences, which is due to the fact that a national repository called “DataverseNO” has been in operation since 2017. For major disciplines, while the U.S. has a large share of data released by its government, other countries also differ in the percentage of data sets released; it is possible that there are differences in the disciplines in which each country has historically focused on data release.

Analysis 2: Current status of data use by research disciplines

For RQ2, we quantitatively and qualitatively analyzed the disciplines in which data-driven research through data publication is active. The first step is to calculate the percentage of papers in each discipline with data citation in 2019, the most recent year with the highest number of data sets loaded. A total of nine disciplines are targeted, those in which data sets registered in DCI are cited more than 2,500 times in WoS papers in total for all years. The second part is to measure the diversity of the disciplines of DCI data set cited by the paper for each discipline of papers. Here, we use the Sterling-Rao Diversity Index, which measures diversity that considers the potential distance between disciplines:

$$\text{Sterling – Rao Diversity Index } D = \sum_{ij(i \neq j)} d_{ij} p_i p_j \quad (1)$$

where p_i is the proportion of discipline i among all cited data set, and d_{ij} is calculated by 1-similarity, which was calculated by dividing the number of data sets to which both discipline i and j were assigned by the sum set of discipline i and j .

In general, the larger the population, the higher the diversity index, so the effect of differences in population size was mitigated by resampling 1000 times with a sample size of 2500, the smallest sample size among the disciplines.

First, the percentage of data citations (percentage of papers that cite at least one data item on the DCI) in each discipline is presented in Table 4 for all papers and for the top 10% most cited papers. However, as previously mentioned, since “self-citations” are included here, this indicator should be interpreted as the progress of data-driven research, including the trend of data publication, rather than pure citation. The results reveal that Crystallography is more advanced in data-driven research than other disciplines, with more than 30% of all papers. Ecology is next with 12%. In six of the nine disciplines, the percentage of papers in the top 10% most cited tends to be statistically significantly higher than that of data citations for the entire paper. The results indicate that papers with high citation count tend to have data citations (including self-citations).

Table 4. Percentage of papers with data citations in each discipline

	Entire paper			Top10% papers only			
	Papers with any data citation	All papers	Rato	Papers with any data citation	All papers	Rato	
Biochemistry & Molecular Biology	1,801	56,419	3.19%	319	6,395	4.99%	***p<0.01
Biodiversity Conservation	399	6,399	6.24%	57	679	8.39%	*p <0.05
Genetics & Heredity	602	21,281	2.83%	129	1,999	6.45%	***p<0.01
Crystallography	1,960	6,274	31.24%	196	634	30.91%	
Geosciences, Multidisciplinary	592	26,965	2.20%	104	3,003	3.46%	***p<0.01
Meteorology & Atmospheric Sciences	441	14,536	3.03%	71	1,480	4.80%	***p<0.01
Multidisciplinary Sciences	1,612	61,635	2.62%	474	6,068	7.81%	***p<0.01
Social Sciences, Interdisciplinary	59	6,684	0.88%	6	789	0.76%	
Ecology	1,635	20,369	8.03%	248	1,981	12.52%	***p<0.01

Next, the Sterling-Rao Diversity Index of disciplines of data cited by the nine WoS paper disciplines is illustrated in Figure 3. The overall results indicate that there are differences in the

use of the disciplines of the databases cited by each discipline. Crystallography is more concentrated than other disciplines, ranging from 0.20 to 0.25. Combined with the results in Table 4, although the citation rate of data sets is high in the 2019 paper disciplines, the disciplines of data sets that are cited are concentrated. Ecology and biodiversity are next, and these also tend to utilize data from specific disciplines. On the other hand, the multidisciplinary sciences and the social and interdisciplinary disciplines are the most diverse, where the data used are also diverse because the disciplines of the papers themselves are interdisciplinary.

Figure 3. Sterling-Rao Diversity index of data cited by papers in each discipline

Discussion

The DCI data were analyzed from various perspectives to gain a cross-disciplinary understanding of the current status of the promotion of data-driven research. The results revealed that countries and disciplines in which Open Data are thriving tend to differ. The U.S., which is promoting Open Data on a national scale, tends to have numerous data sets released in multiple disciplines. Japan has been particularly active in releasing spectroscopic data. On the other hand, the number of data sets in repositories (classified as Multidisciplinary science fields), where researchers can load data regardless of the discipline, has increased rapidly in recent years. In terms of data citation rates, it is particularly active in the discipline of Crystallography, but the disciplines of cited data sets are concentrated. Meanwhile, there are disciplines where data citation rates are low, but the disciplines of databases used are diverse.

This analysis also revealed limitations of the DCI database. The range of data covered by the DCI is biased and further research is needed on how this affects the results of the analysis. For databases of research articles, coverage has also been investigated and it has been shown that the conclusions of the bibliometric analysis depend on the data source and the indicators used. (Herzing et al.,2015; Visser et al.,2021). The same can be said for the analysis of databases of data. In addition to this DCI issue, the lack of established data citation conventions, such as the lack of uniformity in how data are described in papers and other documents when they are cited, and the maintenance of citation information in repositories, have also created problems (Silvello, 2018). Furthermore, the relationship between articles and the accompanying publicly available data also requires conceptual examination. One view is to regard this as 'self-citation' and remove it from the analysis. However, another view, which places the data at the centre, implies that whoever the user is, is the one who used the data. In that case, the data has value

and does not need to be removed, even if it is self-cited. It is necessary to re-examine indicators by examining the concept of data citation itself. Future research should investigate how open data affects research activities from various perspectives.

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